

**CULTURAL INFILTRATION AND PREJUDICE AGAINST
KANNYWOOD FILM INDUSTRY IN ALIYU KAMAL'S
*HAUSA GIRL***

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Abstract

The emergence of Kannywood, a film industry in the late 20th century in Kano State is expected to be heralded for providing an alternative and more indigenous form of entertainment in Northern Nigeria, replacing Indian movies that dominated the region for decades. However, from its inception in the late 90s, Kannywood industry has been receiving backlashes and accusations of corrupting and adulterating authentic Hausa/Islamic culture and traditions. Thus, this paper aims to examine Aliyu Kamal's novel *Hausa Girl* which portrays not only the reception of Kannywood in a conservative society but also its apparent influence on people, culture and tradition. The objectives are to explore the challenges Kannywood actors/actresses face in Hausa society and to investigate whether Kannywood is a threat to Hausa culture and tradition or a tool that can be utilized to advance/preserve authentic Hausa culture in the global era. Employing a qualitative textual analysis, the paper argues that Kannywood movie industry is used as a doormat to criticize immorality and other social vices that have been in existence prior to the creation of the industry. It is revealed that some of the so called elements of Hausa culture that people vehemently accuse the industry of corrupting, are not in tandem with the Islamic principles. Similarly, some of the characters' lifestyle and choices in Kamal's novel further expose the obvious moral decay in the society before the development of the movie industry.

Conclusively, the backlash against Kannywood in conservative North uncovers xenophobic tendencies against cultural infiltration/exchange and globalization.

Keywords: Kannywood, Northern Nigeria, Hausa, Culture, Aliyu Kamal, *Hausa Girl*

Introduction

Apart from being a moral compass that guards a society, literature across the globe has been used as an effective medium of entertainment, education and enlightenment. As such, when Kano market literature began to emerge in the 1980s which gave rise to drama series, it became popular in Hausa land in northern Nigeria. Its acceptability in a conservative Hausa society was not limited to the entertainment it provided, but rather, its success lies in the primary objectives of the drama series. They were used as channels through which the public is enlightened without violating the society's sensibilities. In other words, these dramas were able to educate, enlighten and entertain people without compromising the Hausa cultural norms and values, thus, their unwavering popularity. The essence of these drama series was not to enrich the lives of the actors and actresses financially, but rather used as tools for sensitizing the public especially on matters related to government policies or programs and other relevant issues. Actors and actresses like Samanja Mazan Fama, Golobo, Mai Aya, and Kasimu Yaro, among others, were able to enlighten and entertain the public on current affairs via their acting without tarnishing the image of their culture and religion (Islam). Because of the relevance of these drama series at that time, these actors and actresses were respected and revered in the society. The success of Kano market literature inspired some of the writers to venture into *soyayya* movies based on popular demand. For instance, one of the early *soyayya* movies *in da so da Kauna* was based on the bestseller novel with the same title by Ado Ahmed Gidan Dabino. The success of this movie paved way for the production of subsequent movies in this genre. Movies like *Ki Yarda da Ni* (1996) and *Allura Cikin Ruwa*, among others. Film makers and producers such as Ibrahim Mandawari, Tijjani Ibrahim and Salisu Balarabe, laid the foundation for the emergence of Kannywood movie industry as we know it today, following the huge success and acceptability of the above movies in Hausa society.

As an offshoot of Kano market literature, Kannywood industry was a huge success in the 1990s when it first emerged. This is because the movies strictly adhered to indigenous cultural values and often draw inspiration from Hausa oral traditions which resulted in the creation of movies in which the characters, stories and culture the audience and general public can relate to. Unfortunately, the rise of Islamic fundamentalism in the early 2000s aided in stunting the growth of the industry. This is because, the industry is accused of being a breeding ground for immorality and other social decadence. The condemnation of Kannywood movie industry in Hausa land perhaps may be because of the action of some film makers. Film makers who deviated from portraying stories that resonate with societal values and instead embrace elements of Bollywood movies especially with regards to love songs and dance. Due to this deviation on the part of some of the film makers, Kannywood industry began to lose its credibility in Hausa society. It started receiving backlashes and accusations of corrupting and adulterating authentic Hausa/Islamic culture and traditions.

Hausa Girl by Aliyu Kamal is one of the few works of literature that attempt to depict the reception of Hausa films and generally, the influence of Kannywood movie industry Hausa land, Kano State in particular; a puritan State guided by Sharia'ah and Hausa cultural norms and values. In the novel, the emergence of Hausa movies in northern Nigeria, is projected to negatively influence its ardent viewers especially women. Kamal responds to the emergence of Kannywood industry like the general public. That is, he demonstrates his:

Disenchantment on how the Hausa film industry apes Indian culture to the detriment of Hausa culture, which they distort and, therefore, breach Islamic injunctions, as Indian culture has nothing to do with Islam, (Saje, Mahmud and Bala 2022, p. 107)

This indicates that, Kamal is critical of Kannywood movie industry because he believes, rather than add value to socio-cultural aspect in the society, it gradually destroys Hausa preexisting values and traditions.

It is against this background that this paper seeks to contest the notion that Kannywood movie industry/Hausa films is/are solely responsible for moral

corruption and social vices in Hausa society. While the paper to some extent, shares similar view with Kamal regarding the lack of originality in some Hausa movies, which often limits adequate depiction of authentic Hausa/Islamic values and tradition, as witnessed in its earlier movies in the 1990s, when it comes to moral decay in Hausa society, it argues that, accusing Kannywood movie industry entirely for corrupting Hausa society may be extreme and unrealistic. Criticism and rejection from the public could be one of the major factors that crippled Kannywood even before it is fully developed. Ibrahim (2017) argues that, one of the downfall of the movie industry today is the blatant hypocrisy exhibited by our people. He argues that, Hausa movies and actors are attacked and criticized in the name of protecting cultural and religious heritage of Hausa but the same people patronize Bollywood, Nollywood and Hollywood movies for entertainment. Despite the fact that these foreign movies are in most cases uncensored and promote immorality, they are accepted in our society. Kannywood movies on the other hand, despite practicing some decency especially in terms of dressing and physical contacts among actors/actresses, a censorship board is created to control the contents of the movies. This is done to ensure the movie industry (Kannywood) doesn't succeed in adulterating authentic Hausa and Islamic values. But the question is, can a movie industry which is already laden with restrictions be responsible for corrupting the public? Does this means social vices such as prostitution, gambling, and stealing, among others, were absent in Hausa land before the emergence of Kannywood? Kamal's *Hausa Girl* depicts the reception of Kannywood in Hausa land and thus, an ideal text to analyze in order to answer these questions.

Culture, Cultural Exchange and Identity in the Global Era

Culture is defined by Tyler (1870) cited in Avruch (1998) as a complex whole which includes knowledge, beliefs, arts, morals, laws, customs and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society, (Tyler 1870, p. 1 cited in Avruch 1998, p. 6). This definition indicates that culture is unique and peculiar to a group of people. While biologically humans across the globe are the same, for instance, we eat, give birth, die, among others, each human comes from/belongs to a particular culture that he/she identifies with. Belonging to different cultural groups while maintaining the same human needs is specifically

why Ojaide (2015) argues that culture is a ‘form of adornment to humanity...it is the culmination of a people or group’s ways of life with their beliefs, lifestyle and manner of dealing with their human condition and practiced realities,’ (Ojaide 2015, p. 4). Thus, while humanity is common, culture is specific and unique. It becomes a collective memory/identity that is specially designed for a particular group of people.

Even though culture is unique and peculiar to a group of people, human interact with one another for centuries and often in some cases, migrate from one place to the other. The contact among people ensures cultural exchange, as elements of different cultures blend together to create in some cases, a hybrid culture. As such, throughout history, no culture is able to survive in isolation. This cultural infusion is more prominent today in the digital age as globalization promotes among other things, the intermingling/transfusion of various cultures which leads to the adulteration of certain cultural elements. Various cultures today especially from minority groups are under threat of being subsumed by more dominant cultures. In African context, while it is difficult to erase completely major cultural groups such as Hausa, Zulu or Swahili, among others, by mainstream cultures, the emergence of mediascape in the global era contributes to the gradual effacement/replacement of certain cultural elements with the alien ones. This gradual penetration of dominant foreign cultures into other local cultures especially when the indigenous culture loses some of its values, is what is referred to as cultural infiltration.

While Ngugi (1986) argues that cultural infiltration or ‘cultural bomb’ as he calls it, entails the rapid debasement of African cultural identity via cultural imperialism, globalization today ensures that the infiltration is subtle not forced. For instance, in the colonial era, children were forced to abandon their languages and embrace the foreign ones in schools, (Ngugi 1986). Mediascape today, is the biggest medium of cultural infiltration especially between western and African cultures. Social media such as YouTube and Facebook, music, Netflix, podcasts, among others, are some of the biggest mediascape patronized by African youths today. Consuming western programs/personalities/experiences from such platforms often leads to these youths subconsciously embracing foreign/western cultural values even if such values clash with their authentic culture and tradition.

It is often this fear of cultural adulteration by alien (especially western culture) that trigger condemnation of Kannywood movie industry in Hausa land.

In Hausa society, where the culture is inspired by Islamic values and principles, most forms of western influence especially via mediascape is seen as cultural infiltration and therefore, often avoided/rejected. As noticed earlier, Hausa drama series were tied to the cultural heritage, as such, were appreciated by the audience. However, Kannywood movies began to receive backlash when the public observe elements of foreign cultures allegedly introduced in the movies; the most common ones are romantic songs and sensual dance between the two genders. This created a room for accusing the films/industry for corrupting the youths especially in terms of dressing and obedience. Thus, leading to rapid immorality and a rise in social vices in the society. People often condemn it for being a breeding ground for moral decay, and therefore, only wayward individuals can be actors/actresses.

Similarly, another reason for the poor reception of the movie industry in the society is that, the filmmakers/producers are uncreative and inauthentic. In the novel for instance, the disdain of Kannywood movies is observed in Bala Gano's disregard for the industry. He says:

I have never though well or been favorably disposed to the film venture. Then I watched *Hausa Girl*. It has indeed brought in millions, but I was appalled by the indecent dancing. Generally, I have long been incensed by Kannywood. Film directors project bad morals. They have so far remained amateurish, childish, and pecuniary. The film business is still new. No doubt about that. But it has so far failed to draw lessons on a sound local tradition to serve as a foundation, (HG p. 234).

Bala Gano's argument regarding the lack of originality in Hausa movies may be considered valid with regards to filmmakers such as Sonkowa (SK). Sonkowa is a character depicted in the text as a film maker whose concern is to cast pretty girls in sensual movies of little or no value at all, (HG, p206). Sonkowa represents some Kannywood film makers who lack original concept and basic knowledge in film production. Ibrahim (2017) observes that, such film makers though lack

originality, continue to ‘substantially copy, imitate, transmute, and plagiarize Bollywood films with impunity,’ (Ibrahim 2017, p. 78). Like Sonkowa, the aim of the film makers is financial gain not promoting authentic Hausa culture. Thus, filmmakers like Sonkowa produce sensual movies with the intention of attracting more audience (and profit). While such movies in some cases ‘brought in millions,’ (HG p. 234) as Bala Gano observes, they also attract contempt, as some of the audience, Islamic scholars and the general public criticize the concept of adaptation (most of Bollywood) and remake Kannywood embraces. Despite adapting or copying from Bollywood movies, accusing the entire industry of promoting immorality while ignoring other social and cultural vices may not be true. The industry is depicted in the text to serve as a gateway for bad behavior and immorality. Such condemnation prevents constructive criticism or personal introspection/reflection from growing. A close analysis of Hajjo Gano’s character reveals that Kannywood has little effect on her personality. Loneliness (from absence of biological parents) and idleness, often influence her behavior.

While as noticed earlier, Kannywood film makers are often criticized for deviating from the norm, the condemnation of the industry hides a fear of cultural infiltration from alien culture. In his *Decolonization of the Mind*, Ngugi explains that fear of change emanates from the effect of psychological violence during colonialism, (Ngugi 1986). In Hausa land today, there is generally, a fear of change. As a response to the ‘cultural bomb’ during colonialism, people are afraid of losing their cultural identity to western influence, thus, lose their Islamic values too. This fear of change influence the rejection of Kannywood movie industry as depicted in Kamal’s *Hausa Girl*.

Kannywood Movie Industry and Moral Corruption in Kamal’s *Hausa Girl*

Hausa Girl is a novel by Kamal that explores the influence of Kannywood movie industry in a conservative society. Set in Kano state, northern Nigeria, the story revolves around Hajjo Gano - a young lady who nourishes the dream of becoming a successful actress in Kannywood film industry. Through her journey into Kannywood as an actress, the story exposes the impact of the film industry not just on the youths but on the socio-cultural aspects in the society. The negative impact of Hausa movies is embodied in the lifestyle of the protagonist- Hajjo Gano; a Hausa girl who becomes socially and morally corrupt as a result of

excessive view of the movies. Her corrupt character is further amplified when she meets Sonkowa (SK), a film producer, who fulfils her dream of becoming a Kannywood actress. Rather than safeguard her dignity, Hajjo Gano is portrayed to be wearing indecent dressing and dancing sensually in order to attract more audience. Her decision to be an actress leads to her fallout with Uncle Ilu and his family (her surrogate family) because Uncle Ilu (and the general public) believe that 'Hausa films are amoral; they won't impart anything good to you,' (HG, p. 85). Kannywood movie industry is rejected by the general public for deviating from socio-cultural norms and values in Hausa land but embracing foreign and immoral values such as lewd dancing and singing. In the end Hajjo Gano losses everything as a result of her choices. Sonkowa hypnotize and raped her then kills her father Bala Gano. Kabir Badayi (KB) leaves her for Zeenat Amin.

After realizing she losses everything- her father, SK and acting, in a desperate attempt to belong, Hajjo Gano asks KB whether he will marry her as the right thing to do since she is alone with no family and most importantly, because he loves her. Instead of accepting her offer, he spits violently at her feet to indicate his disgust at the idea of marriage between them. KB's choice to disown Hajjo Gano despite being aware that she is a victim of SK's exploitation/manipulation, exposes the vulnerability of women in a society that tends to ignore their plight as victims of circumstance but punishes them immediately after a mistake. Women's value is weighed based on their character/personality. An ideal woman is the one who is docile, religious and unexposed to immorality. This preference is witnessed when KB decides to marry Zeenat Amin instead of Hajjo Gano. He explains that:

She [Zeenat] excels you in everything. For me, Zeenat's beauty ranks a lowly second to her beautiful manners... what about you? You may be beautiful but you are a degenerate empty head. As SK's leftover, you can disappear from the face of the earth for all I care, (HG, p. 249)

To KB, Zeenat is the perfect wife because she is untainted unlike Hajjo Gano who despite the fact that he is aware she is hypnotized and raped by SK, chooses to abandon her for her 'impurity'. This type of punishment is not usually

experienced by the male gender. While women like Hajjo Gano are condemned for a wrong choice, men like Uncle Ilu, Bala Gano and Alhaji Baba, get away with immorality that they partake in willingly, simply because they have 'repented'. For instance, Uncle Ilu in his youthful days 'wined and gambled with sex workers in Sabon Gari,' (HG, p. 26). He only becomes sober and remorseful when the money he inherits from his father disappears. However, despite his choices, he becomes one of the most respected man in his community after his repentance. In Hausa land as depicted in the novel, there is a disparity between men and women when it comes to waywardness. Women are expected to always embody good character and conduct while the men though may be criticized for a bad behavior, they are generally immune from stigmatization or condemnation. Though Kannywood is generally abhorred, the treatment of actors differ based on gender. Hajjo Gano is immediately rejected by Uncle Ilu and her extended family simply for acting in a movie. Kabir Badayi on the other hand, as an aspiring film producer, is not only immune but is also able to marry a descent girl from a respectable family. Similarly, Sonkowa is a film producer who is notorious for sexually abusing young actresses and producing sensual movies, despite the sanction against Kannywood industry, SK moves freely without fear of retribution from government or the public. Thus, when women such as Hajjo Gano or Hanne express desire to become actresses, it is not only due to watching excessive movies, but out of vulnerability that film producers like SK exploit. Hausa movies are not responsible for initiating such biased punishment between men and women in Hausa land. It rather stems from the Hausa cultural believe that chastity is reserved only for women and not for both gender. It is precisely due to this patriarchal concept in Hausa culture that Uncle Ilu, Bala Gano, Alhaji Bala and to some extent, Kabir Badayi, are able to escape moral repercussion while Hajjo Gano, her mother and Hanne, couldn't escape punishment for their 'wayward' behavior.

On another note, Hausa movies are condemned by the public because as often claimed, they are always responsible for moral decay in the society. This idea is disputed here because based on the analysis of the text, there are several instances to indicate that moral decay is not to some extent imported by Kannywood industry but by the personal choice of the some of the characters and ironically, foreign influence. This is captured perfectly in the character of Bala Gano. It is

suggested that, he meets and falls in love with a ‘prostitute’ in a brothel (Hajjo Gano’s mother) during the period that Kannywood movie industry is not in existence. The only form of entertainment comes from watching foreign movies. It is depicted that:

His friends convince him to visit Sabon Gari red-light district. It was after they had watched a double feature film at the El Dorado Cinema one night- a western and an Indian. He had been titillated by the erotic scenes in *Once Upon a Time in the West* and the lascivious dancing and singing in *Sanyasi*, which had fired hormonal urges that he agreed with his friends could be blunted by way of illicit sex, (HG, p. 4)

The above instance indicates that the so called foreign movies of Hollywood and Bollywood, have done more damage to societal values than Kannywood movies (that is not in existence) when Bala Gano is in his youthful age.

Similarly, Hausa movies in the text, are mainly criticized for importing alien culture such as lewd dancing and sensual scenes. As these movies are condemned, people patronize other foreign movies which in most cases, don’t adhere to both Hausa and Islamic values and are entirely different from Hausa in terms of language and sensibility. For instance, Nana, like most of the characters in the novel, believes Kannywood is immoral and doesn’t represent Hausa culture but she watches Bollywood movies that are unfiltered. It is explained that:

Nana wasn’t very keen about Hausa films, but she was passionate about Indian movies shown on the satellite channel. Zee Aflam showed films twenty four hours a day and had among the most faithful viewers in northern Nigeria married and unmarried women alike, (HG, p. 121).

If Hausa films are immoral for employing elements of foreign and unislamic values, why should Bollywood and Hollywood movies be embraced by the public comfortably? Such behavior exposes the double standard exhibited by the public when it comes to their film preference. As argued earlier, the blind patronage of

foreign movies which are uncensored and clearly unislamic, by northern Nigerian people while rejecting Hausa films for employing fraction of foreign culture, comes from a place of hypocrisy and unpatriotism. Like Nana, Bala Gano enjoys condemning Hausa films as he calls them:

Crude films lacking development...half of the movies are 'always wasted on passionate but senseless, mindless and artless dancing by ill-mannered and sweaty boys and girls jumping up and down without fitness, without grace. Such trash short changes me, the viewer ... I never tire watching good storyline fine acting witty dialogue and beautiful photography like in *Silverado* and Serge Leone's *Once Upon a Time in the West* (HG, p. 235).

Such disregard for indigenous movies in favor of western movies may be due to the rippling effect of cultural bomb/cultural imperialism which Ngugi (1986) explains to project African indigenous culture as backward, while European values as symbol of progress. This type of colonial mentality is captured in Okot p'Bitek's 'Song of Lawino' where Ocol and Clementine though Africans, embrace European culture at the detriment of their African values and tradition. People like Bala Gano and Nana feel when a movie is foreign, it is automatically better than Hausa movie despite the fact that these characters understand Hausa language used in the movies and can relate to the sensibility projected in those movies.

Furthermore, Kannywood industry receives heavy backlash and criticism for apparently producing movies that promote alien cultures that are not in tandem with the Islamic principles. Drawing from some of the portrayals in the text however, the paper argues that, most of the so called Hausa cultural values that people vehemently accuse the industry of corrupting, are not remotely related to Islamic teachings. One of such instances is depicted in the relationship between husband and wife in a typical Hausa setting. It is portrayed in the novel that men in the land hardly sit to chat with their women. This is demonstrated in the character of Fatahiya's husband and Uncle Ilu. In fact, it is tradition that children often visit a new bride's home (because she's lonely) to entertain her in the absence of her husband. This is because a married man:

Hardly indulges his wife or wives by staying with them for hours on end discussing low brow family concerns when male companionship is the better gentlemanly option, (HG, p. 20)

It is ironic that an act that is considered sacred in Hausa culture is actually discouraged in Islam. When men are often absent in the lives of their family, indiscipline or evil easily strife. For example, in the bride's house, Hajja Gano recalls how the boys play a game of smoke where they peel a cornstalk and set it with fire. When they graduate from alighting a cornstalk, they start smoking 'the real thing by picking the filter discarded by adults and smoking the small piece of remaining tobacco,' (HG, p. 22). With the advent of Kannywood movies, housewives such as Fatahiyya and grown up girls who are too old to visit a new bride's house, pass away their time watching such movies. In Islam, for children to be morally sound, their fathers need to spend more time with them instead of neglecting the family in the name of tradition. Thus, Hausa people whose culture is often influenced by Islamic principles and tradition need to inculcate the Islamic tradition of strong bond between parents and their children so as to prevent/minimize the influence of immorality and other social vices among the children.

Another important aspect portrayed in the text, is the issue of forced marriage. The concept of forced marriage have been exploited by various writers in northern Nigeria in order to expose its psychological and sometimes physical effects on women who are mostly the victims of this act. In most cases, this type of marriage leads to prostitution. The victims run away from home and due to lack of support, they are forced into prostitution in order to survive. Such act is witnessed in novels like Ibrahim Sheme's *Yartsana* where Zainab the protagonist rebels against forced marriage by becoming a prostitute, and in Razinat T. Mohammed's *Habiba*, where though Habiba does not run away from home, her rebellion is in becoming a lesbian. Apart from experiencing psychological torture, these victims are out rightly rejected by both their family and the society which often leads to misery or tragedy. For instance, in the case of Zainab, she contracted HIV/AIDS and died alone while Firdausi in Nawal El Sadawi's *Women at Point Zero*, kills a man (Marfuz; her pimp) and end up in prison on death row.

In Hausa culture and tradition, children are expected to obey the will of their parents without objection as any form of questioning is met with corporal punishment as witnessed in the relationship between Uncle Ilu and his family or in severe case, banishment from the family as in the case of Bala Gano who is disowned by his father for marrying a former prostitute. While forced marriage is normalized in Hausa land, it is strictly prohibited in Islam due to the psychological trauma the victims may find themselves in. Kannywood films are accused of promoting immorality such as prostitution in the society. A close up analysis of the text however, reveals that, Hausa tradition of forced marriage have done more harm in the society than Hausa movies. Kamal explores the issue of forced marriage and how it negatively affect the victims in the novel under study. The portrayal is similar to the ones depicted in his other works such as *No Sweat* in which Ladiyo becomes a prostitute to avoid being forced to marry a man she abhors and in his *Fire in my Backyard* where the character of Tala does the same as Ladiyo. In *Hausa Girl*, the psychological effect of forced marriage is encapsulated in the life of Hajjo Gano's mother who becomes a prostitute after running away from home due to pressure to marry a man she does not love and Fatahiyya, who seeks solace in Hausa romantic novels and films as coping mechanism.

In Hajjo Gano's mother's case, her decision to become a prostitute becomes a tragedy that does not only affect her alone but its rippling effect is felt by Bala Gano and their daughter Hajjo Gano. Bala meets and falls in love with Hajjo Gano's mother at 'the red light district of Sabon Gari,' (HG, p 5), but because Hausa society rejects such women and deemed them unmarriageable, the union between Bala and Hajjo Gano's mother is rejected by Grandfather (Bala's father). The concept of repentance/forgiveness is not applied to such women. That is to say, once a prostitute always a prostitute (thus, not ideal for marriage). For instance, Grandfather was 'adamant in his refusal to let the erring lovers rectify their 'misdeed' even by resorting to the dictates of the Sharia'ah against whose reforming conditions the devout old man dared not stand,' (HG, p 5). Because Bala disobeys his father by marrying a former prostitute, Grandfather rejects not only Bala but his family (his wife and Hajjo Gano). His intense hatred for the union is witnessed in his refusal to bless Hajjo Gano when she is born (he labels her a bastard), his nonchalant attitude towards the death of Hajjo Gano's mother

and holds grudge against any family member that supports Bala Gano. It is precisely Grandfather's attitude that leads to the tragic death of Hajjo Gano's mother. Due to stigmatization, she suffers from tension and high blood pressure which leads to excessive bleeding during labor, thus, killing her, (HG, p. 10). In Fatahiya's case, she is forced to marry a man she does not love, but unlike Hajjo's mother, Fatahiyya agrees to marry the man chosen for her out of obedience. Her parents disregard her opinion and instead choose Alhaji Baba; a man with three wives already, for their own personal interest, (HG, p. 41). Instead of running away, Fatahiyya stays, but numbs her sadness by reading novels and Kannywood movies, as coping mechanism.

Condemning Kannywood movie industry because it promotes social vices such as prostitution is disputed. As depicted in the text, the main culprit responsible for promoting immorality may be forced marriage and not entirely Hausa films. These movies today act like the children who visit a new bride's house to keep her company, entertain lonely housewives and other idle individuals in the society. Therefore, rather than accusing the industry of going astray from the teaching of the holy Prophet in Islam, Hausa society needs to discard certain patriarchal cultural elements and embrace the true teaching of Islam especially on the concept of force marriage and with regards to how husbands interact with their wives and children. For immorality and other social vices such as prostitution to be effectively wiped out from Hausa land, then certain practices such as forced marriage need to be sanctioned not Hausa movies.

While this paper agrees that some Kannywood film makers are only preoccupied with financial gain as opposed to earlier actors/actresses of Hausa drama series, the condemnation of the entire movie industry as a breeding ground for immorality in the society, is superficial. This is observed in the manner in which authentic Hausa culture and Kannywood industry are depicted in the text. Kamal employs a form of 'Manichean system' as espoused by Fanon (1961) to depict the culture and industry. Hausa culture is to some extent, glorified, depicted as pristine and perfect while Kannywood industry on the other hand is condemned as corrupt and alien. The depiction of the Hausa culture as perfect while Kannywood industry as a harbinger of evil as portrayed in this novel, reiterates what Achebe (1965) warns writers to avoid. That is, a writer will defeat his purpose if he is:

Suspected of glossing over inconvenient past. We cannot pretend that our past was one long, technicolour idyll. We have to admit that like any other people's past ours has its good as well as its bad sides, (Achebe, 1965, p. 158).

In this case, it is obvious some elements of Hausa culture and tradition such as the concept of forced marriage and stigmatization of 'erring' women give raise to social vices and moral corruption as opposed to excessive exposure to Hausa movies. Even though the author succeeds in criticizing some of the issues prevalent in northern Nigeria, such as forced marriage, for instance, by implying that it may leads to prostitution, he falls short in identifying other Hausa cultural elements like the strain relationship between husband and wife, among others, often contribute to moral decay in the society. Instead, Hausa movies and romantic novels are squarely blamed for the downfall of morality in Hausa land as depicted in the novel. Defending the preservation of Hausa values and tradition especially in an era that promotes cultural integration, is valid. However, projecting the culture as pristine and perfect as portrayed in *Hausa Girl* is a form of romanticizing our past (in this context authentic Hausa culture) while Kannywood movie industry is the villain, responsible for perforating Hausa cultural value. Such depictions lead to a biased and superficial representation of the two aspects. No culture is perfect or independent without the influence of other cultures. As explained earlier, mediascape makes this cultural exchange easier. As such, whether Kannywood exist today or not, Hausa culture is bound to shift and adjust under the influence of globalization. Kannywood movies today have come to stay. Therefore, rather than condemning or projecting these movies as morally corrupt and irrelevant, as depicted in Kamal's novel, they should be utilized to preserve and globalized Hausa language and culture. Similarly, there is a need for the film makers/producers to have a 'homecoming' as espoused by Ojaide (2015), into the Hausa folklore, in order to adequately depict/represent authentic Hausa culture that the audience will relate to instead of slavishly and excessively borrowing from foreign (especially Bollywood) culture to produce their movies. When Hausa movies that depict the people's sensibility are created, they become effective tools used to combat social vices, crude cultural practices

such as force marriage and immorality imported by foreign influence such as indecent dressing and lewd music and dance.

Conclusion

Since culture is always in a flux, constantly evolving as people evolve, it is possible to embrace change without losing one's cultural identity. As depicted in Kamal's novel, the backlash against Kannywood movie industry in conservative North comes from a place of fear. Historically, colonialism brought about cultural imperialism whereby paramount importance is placed on western/European culture and tradition against African culture (Hausa) like replacing Tsangaya system of education with western education, Hausa language with English and Islam with Christianity (though Christianity is not widely accepted). Today, Kannywood movies can be used as medium of projecting authentic Hausa culture and experience instead of being condemned as breeding ground for immorality. From the analysis of the text, it is revealed that some of the cultural elements that Kannywood movies are accused of corrupting, clash with Islamic teaching. Thus, instead of blaming Hausa movies and actors squarely, for moral decay in the society, cultural elements such as force marriage need to be addressed effectively in literature and society at large. Conclusively, criticism of the industry as portrayed in *Hausa Girl* uncovers xenophobic tendencies against cultural infiltration/exchange in an era of globalization

References

- Achebe, C. (1965). The Novelist as a Teacher, 103-106, in Quayson, A. & Olaniyan, T. (eds) (2007). *African Literature Anthology of Criticism and Theory*, Victoria, Blawell Publisher,
- Avruch, K. (1998). *Culture and Conflict Resolution*. Washington DC: United States Institute of Peace Press
- El-Sadawi, N. (1983). *Women at Point Zero*. London: Zed Books
- Ibrahim, M. M. (2017). Originality in Absentia: A Study of Selected Kannywood Films, Abdulraheem, H.A. Aliyu, S.B. and Akano, R.K. (Eds) (2017). *Literature, Integration and Harmony in Northern Nigeria*, 72-85

- Kamal, A. (2004). *A Fire in My Backyard*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Kamal, A. (2010). *Hausa Girl*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd.
- Kamal, A. (2013). *No Sweat*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd
- Ngugi, W.T. (1986). *Decolonizing the Mind: the Politics of Language in African Literature*. London: James Curry Heinemann
- Ojaide, T., (2015). *Indigeneity, Globalization and African Literature: Personally Speaking*. US: Palgrave McMillan,
- P'Bitek, O. (1966). *Song of Lawino*. Kampala: East African Publishing House
- Saje, U, Mahmud, I, Bala, N. (2022). *The Novels of Aliyu Kamal: A Critical Perspective*. Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press Ltd
- Sheme, I. (2003). *Yartsana*. Kaduna: Infomart Publishers Ltd.

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